

Inorganic Phosphate Textile Reinforced Cement composite moulds

J. Blom¹, P. Van Itterbeeck¹, J. Van Ackeren¹, J. Wastiels¹

¹ VUB in Brussels -Faculty of Engineering,
Department of Mechanics of Materials and Constructions,
Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels, Belgium,
e-mail: johan.blom@vub.ac.be

SUMMARY

Thermoplastics offer a number of important advantages over thermosetting composites. To produce thermoplastic composite parts, high temperature is needed, so new mould construction techniques need to be developed. In this experimental study a production process is presented using textile reinforced inorganic phosphate cement composite moulds. This technique will be used in a test case to produce moulds for thermoplastic composites.

Keywords: inorganic phosphate cement (IPC); textile reinforced concrete (TRC); moulds; thermoplastic; prototype; high temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Through the early 1970's the composite industry experienced significant growth, this was driven by a demand to meet both styling needs and weight reduction of construction parts. In a market dominated by thermosetting composites, new processing techniques need to be developed, in order to meet the new demands of the industry (ref.:1&2). Driven by the need to produce faster, thermoplastic composites seem to be the future. Thermoplastics offer a number of important advantages over thermo sets like better toughness and damage tolerance, rapid fabrication cycle and the possibility of assembling substructures by welding. Theoretically thermoplastics are an interesting alternative, but processing a material that requires 200°C or even higher with conventional thermo set moulds seems impossible (ref.:3). In order to produce large thermoplastic composite parts, for example ships or windmill blades, new mould construction techniques need to be developed. This research will present a mould technique to replace the conventional metal and thermo harder moulds. The novelty of this technique will be the textile reinforced cement composite, which is used to produce a mould. Basically the TRC is a combination of inorganic phosphate cement (IPC) and random distributed chopped glass fibre textile reinforcement. IPC was developed at the "Vrije Universiteit Brussel" and is commercially available under the name Vubonite[®]. This material is an inorganic, non-alkaline resin, prepared by mixing a powder and a liquid component. The cementitious material is processed in the same way as a polymer resin. Processing time is adjustable and varies from a few minutes to approximately an hour. Hardening occurs spontaneously at room temperature and results in cement with a neutral pH after hardening. Therefore, the glass fibres are not chemically attacked by the cementitious matrix, making the use of traditional E-glass fibres possible. By using

a fibre volume fraction which exceeds the critical fibre volume fraction, the fibres can ensure strength and stiffness at applied loads far exceeding the range at which matrix multiple cracking occurs. (ref.:4) Textile reinforced cementitious composites with glass fibres as reinforcement exhibit relatively high strength and ductility and thus provides an interesting new material for thin shells. Typical data for the pure resin, as well as for composites with unidirectional (UD) or random glass fibre reinforcement can be found in Table I.

TABLE I: properties for the pure IPC, as well as for composites with unidirectional (UD) or random glass fibre reinforcement IPC; after VUBONITE® technical data sheet, (ref.: 5)

		Pure	UD 300 g/m ²	Mat 300 g/m ²
Specific gravity (wet)	kg/dm ³	1.9	2.0	2.0
Specific gravity (dry)	kg/dm ³	1.6	1.75	1.75
Thickness laminate	mm/layer		0.9	0.9
Compressive strength	MPa	60	60	60
Tensile strength	MPa	10	100	30
Stiffness (E- modulus)	GPa	18	7-25	3-20
Coeff. Thermal expansion	8 e -6 /K			
Coeff. Heat conduction	+/- 1 W/mK			
Specific heat	0.8 J/gK			
Fire safety	Absolutely incombustible European clas A1			

Another interesting property is that IPC can resist high temperatures, without releasing toxic gases. This material is also incombustible, according to the European standard EN13501-1. All these advantages make IPC an ideal material to develop a TRC mould which can be produced relatively fast and be used at high temperatures and this all without complex production tools.

The production method of the TRC mould is based on the well known composite hand lay up method, but without releasing toxic gases and the possibility of cleaning the production tools with water. In this case the mould is developed to produce only a few prototype parts, using a prepreg in a closed mould. This study is performed to assess the potential of TRC moulds, and to set up a structure for the future work.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The experimental program was divided into two main groups of experiments. The materials and mixture proportions are described in detail in one part, the experiments related to the influence of temperature in the other.

Materials used for the Mould production

A. Matrix

The matrix used in this study is a mixture of a calcium silicate powder and a phosphate acid based solution of metal oxides. The weight ratio liquid to powder is 1/0,8.

To improve the workability and the specific needs, different fillers were added to the mixture in various amounts. A series of tests was performed to determine the optimal quantity of filler. In this research fumed silica (AEROSIL® FUMED SILICA A200) and zircon (Dupont) were used.

The results of the tests are listed in the table below (table II).

TABLE II: overview of the workability of the matrix

mixture	liquid	powder	filler		mixing	spreading
			fumed silica (AEROSIL® Fumed Silica A200)	Zircon (Dupont)		
01 ipc-100-80	100	80	0	0	++	--
02 ipc-100-80-2	100	80	2	0	++	--
03 ipc-100-80-6	100	80	6	0	++	-
04 ipc-100-80-8	100	80	8	0	+	+
05 ipc-100-80-10	100	80	10	0	-	++
06 ipc-100-80-12	100	80	12	0	--	++
07 ipc-100-80-08	100	80	0	8	++	-
08 ipc-100-80-20	100	80	0	20	+	+
09 ipc-100-80-100	100	80	0	100	-	++
10 ipc-100-80-140	100	80	0	140	--	++

The components are mixed using a “Heidolph RZR 2102” overhead mixer. The mixing is performed in two stages: first the liquid and the powder are mixed at 250 rpm until the powder is mixed into the fluid, after which the speed is increased to 2000 rpm. The fresh IPC mixture being acidic, it chemically attacks most types of metal. To avoid corrosion, the spindle of the mixer is made of stainless steel, while other production tools are in PVC.

The workability is defined as the ease of mixing and spreading of the matrix. Without filler, the matrix presents a low viscosity of around 2000 mPas. Mixing of the component is very easy (++) as shown in the photo below (fig.: 1)

Figure 1: workability of matrix without filler

The matrix is however not covering the surface of the substrate uniformly, and flows from a surface which is not perfectly horizontal (--). By adding filler the matrix becomes less liquid, which makes it possible to cover the master mould. Two different fillers were tested in this study. The workability of each mixture was tested by performing a mixing and spreading test. With each mixture a corner of the master mould was laminated. These laminates were placed in an oven at 300°C to test the heat

resistance and also to determine the surface state. For the first set of experiments AEROSIL® was added to the standard mixture. By adding 6 % of AEROSIL® filler compared to the weight of liquid component, the primary mixing becomes more difficult, as shown in the picture below (fig.:2 left).

Figure 2: workability of matrix with 6% filler compared to the weight of liquid component

After a few minutes of mixing, the mixture will however become uniform, but presents a higher plastic viscosity. The increased yield stress of the mixture makes it possible to apply it on inclined surfaces with a uniform covering (fig.: 2 right). Adding a high amount of filler results in a very sticky paste, which is only applicable using a brush instead of a roller. The primary mixing becomes almost impossible 12 % or more of the filler is added. The addition of 8 % of filler is considered to give the best balance between ease of mixing, and spreading characteristics, and will thus further on be used in this study. The pictures below (fig.: 3) illustrate the difference in aspects between the matrix with an addition of 0% and 8 % of filler compared to the weight of liquid component.

Figure 3: workability of matrix with 0% and 8 % filler compared to the weight of liquid component

For the second set of experiments Zircon was added to the standard mixture. By adding zircon in amounts starting from 8% up to 140 % the workability dramatically changed, as shown in the figure below (fig.:4).

Figure 4: workability of matrix with 8% and 140 % zircon filler compared to the weight of liquid component

By adding 140 % zircon compared to the weight of liquid component, the matrix becomes a paste. This paste is ideal to cover the inclined surfaces of the master mould.

B. Fibres

The E-glass fibre reinforcements used in the composite moulds are chopped glass fibre mats with a fibre density of 300g/m² (type Vetrotex M 5 -300),

C. Surfacing veil

A surfacing veil is used as first layer to get a better surface quality (finishing) and to prevent the glass fibres from penetrating through the matrix top surface. Two types of surfacing veils are tested. One of the tested veils is water dissolvable (Owens Corning, type?), resulting in a better workability. The water dissolvable veil was used to solve the moulding problems, especially in the mould corners. Another advantage of using a surface veil is a significant reduction cracks when the composite is heated.

Temperature range:

In order to start up the experimental program a temperature range must be selected. The most commonly used high temperature thermoplastic polymers for thermoplastic composites are listed in table III. The classification is based on the maximum service temperature of the polymers, which in turn is based on the Glass Transition (T_g) temperature. This is the temperature at which the amorphous portion of the polymer changes from a glassy to a rubbery phase on heating and the process temperature.

Table III - High Temperature Thermoplastics (ref.:6)

Matrix		T _g (°C)	Process Temp (°C)
PP	Polypropylene	-10	175
PEI	Polyetherimide	215	300
PEEK	Polyetheretherketone	143	390
PEKK	Polyetherketonketone	156	340
PPS	Polyphenylene sulphide	90	300
PA-6	Polyamide 6	48	220
PA-12	Polyamide 12	52	190

In this research thermoplastic prepregs will be used. For the first preliminary test TEPEX® dynalite 102-RG600(x)/47% Roving Glass – PA 6 Consolidated Composite Laminate produced by Bond laminates was used. Within the TEPEX® composite laminate, Polyamide 6 is a resin which can be used at temperatures ranging from -30°C to 120°C. PA 6 is known for its toughness, stiffness, abrasion resistance, heat and chemical resistances. Roving E-Glass fibres have an excellent impact performance. This makes the composite material tough and fatigue resistant while offering excellent mechanical properties. The forming temperature of TEPEX is situated between 240°C and 260°C (ref.:7).

Effect of temperature

The influence of temperature was determined by heating up TRC test specimens. The specimens were produced on a master mould using different mixtures of matrix and a chopped glass fibre mat. The photos below illustrate the effect of heating (300°C) on the TRC specimens with different amounts of AEROSIL® filler (figure 5). The first picture on the left illustrates the condition of the surface when no AEROSIL® was added after

heating. The matrix is cracked and in some parts scaled. The second and third photo presents the result of the surface of the specimens with 6 and 8 % AEROSIL®. The surface condition of the sample with 8 % AEROSIL® is acceptable. When adding more filler, more and wider cracks will develop in the surface, as can be clearly seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: result of heating at 300°C, specimens with 0%, 2%, 4%,6%, 8% and 12% AEROSIL®.

The same experiment was performed in the case of the zircon filler. In the picture below we can see the difference between a sample with addition of 20 %, 100% and 180% of zircon filler (fig.:6). By adding between 100 and 180 % zircon the surface showed less cracks after heating. Nonetheless, adding more than 140 % off filler makes the matrix paste more sticky in the fresh state, as thus hindering the laminating procedure.

Figure 6: result of heating at 300°C, specimens with 20%, 100%, 140% and 180% zircon.

MOULD MAKING

The method used in this paper was based on thermoforming stamping. Thermoforming stamping is a low-pressure process that uses consolidated sheets. The method uses a set of two moulds. The process of mould making is described in the following part.

Copying a master mould

The master model is the first requirement to make a mould. This is the original part that is to be copied. The master mould must be coated with several layers of mould release wax “Moldwax 60-x3 Jost Chemicals”. Between each coat of wax the mould has to be polished.

Production of the textile reinforced moulds

The moulds are produced using a hand lay up technique. In the first case study a mixture of IPC was used with the addition of 2% AEROSIL® (% to the weight of the liquid component). In addition two other moulds were also produced, one with 8 % AEROSIL® and another with 140 % zircon (% to the weight of the liquid component). For each IPC matrix layer an average consumption of 900 g/m² was used. The water dissolvent veil is spread out on the master mould. The next step in the production is adding the matrix on top of the veil. By using a deaerating roller or a brush the trapped air is pushed out (fig.:7). After this step a layer of fibre glass mat (Vetrotex M5-300) is applied, followed by matrix which is equally spread out over the surface. It is important that the bonded surface of the fibre mat is facing up. The fibre mat is firmly pressed into the matrix using a roller or by pressing by hand, to prevent trapped air bubbles and insure a good impregnation of the fibre mat (fig.: 7). In total four layers of glass fibres are applied. Finally the mould is packed in a plastic foil, thus preventing evaporation of water. Like most cementitious mixtures, the strength of IPC increases with time (curing). At first the mould is placed in ambient conditions for 24 hours. The curing effect can however be accelerated by heating the mould at 60°C during at least 24 hours. During the curing, both sides of the laminate are covered with plastic to prevent early evaporation of water.

Figure 7: placing the surface veil and the chopped random fibre glass mat

This procedure was repeated to produce the female mould.

Preheating of the mould

The moulds were placed in an oven at 260°C (10°C above processing temperature of the used prepreg) before it was used. This preheating was performed to stabilize the mould. The picture below shows the surface of the preheated male mould (fig.:8).

Figure 8: The surface of the male mould after pre heating at 260°C

MAKING A THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE PART

Mould assembly

The setup of the mould is shown in the photo below (fig.:9).

Figure 9: assembly of the mould setup.

Production process

The prepreg sheet “TEPEX® dynalite 102-RG600(x)/47% Roving Glass – PA 6” was placed between the two moulds. On top of the male mould an infill was placed, in order to transfer the additional mass. The mould assembly was placed in an oven at 250°C for 2 h. After the heating the mould stayed in the oven till room temperature was reached. Due to the pressure and heating the prepreg has deformed to the final shape, as shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: deformed prepreg after heating process.

The last step in the process was the separation of the mould and the composite part.

Results

The possibility of forming a prepreg in textile reinforced cement using a thermoforming stamping method was tested on three moulds using different fillers. For the first test a mould with 2 % AEROSIL® filler was used as matrix. The final part and the state of the used male mould are presented in the photo below (fig.: 11a).

Figure 11a : produced prepreg part and used male mould (2% AEROSIL® FUMED SILICA)

A flat surface could be produced without problems but at the corners some matrix sticks on the final part. The second mould was produced using 140% zircon. The demoulding of the prepreg was possible. When looking at the photo below it is clear that almost no matrix sticks on the final part. The demoulding temperature and timing is crucial in this process. In the second attempt we demoulded the prepreg at +/- 80°C. Another problem is the pressure and temperature distribution in the mould, this is visible in the photo below (fig.:11b). One of the possible explanations can be found in the load quantity and the way it is applied. Additional information about the internal mould temperature could reveal the cause of this problem.

Figure 11b : produced prepreg part and used male mould (140% zircon)

In the last test a mould was produced using 8 % of AEROSIL® filler. The prepreg was heated at 250°C for 2 h, as in the previous tests. After this heating and deforming process, the final part was released from the mould. The demoulding temperature was +/- 80° C. In the surface of the final part almost no matrix residue could be observed. The pressure and temperature distribution was better than in the second experiment, but is still not optimal (fig.:11 c).

Figure 11c : produced prepreg part and used male mould (8 % AEROSIL® FUMED SILICA)

CONCLUSION

The presented technique to produce a thermoforming stamping mould using textile reinforced cement showed some potential. The quality of the produced prepreg parts is related to the composition of the TRC mould and also the production method. This research showed the effect of filler on the workability of the matrix and the surface

quality of the mould after heating. By using a water dissolvable surface veil less cracks were observed when heated.

The first mould with 2 % AEROSIL® was chosen because it has a good workability and penetrates with ease through the fibre mats. In the corners the matrix thickness was too high which results in cracks when heated at elevated temperatures, this due to the lack of fibres. This was clearly illustrated by parts of the matrix sticking on the prepreg after demoulding. When using 8 % AEROSIL® a good balance between workability and impregnation of the fibres was obtained. The result was a mould capable to produce the best prepreg part of the tested moulds. When using 140 % zircon filler the impregnation of all the fibres became more difficult. The experiments also showed the importance off the right demoulding temperature and timing. One of the remaining problems seems to be the distribution of pressure and temperature in the mould. In general we can conclude that forming a prepreg “TEPEX® dynalite 102-RG600(x)/47% Roving Glass – PA 6” at 250°C was possible with a textile reinforced mould using inorganic phosphate cement in combination with a filler. The optimal mould however must still be developed/optimised.

FUTURE WORK

The future work involves the optimisation of the TRC composite at high temperature. The aim is to tune the composite so that it would have a good workability in combination with strength and high temperature resistance. To improve the mould surface quality, it is important to optimize the curing process to reduce shrinkage, in order to reduce cracks. Another solution for the surface quality problem could be the use of high temperature resisting mould release agents or coatings. These prelim tests were preformed using one type of prepreg, other types need to be tested. Finally the proposed moulding technique could be used in a project, in order to produce large thermoplastic composite parts, for example ships or windmill blades.

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